

1 **Making bioinformatics training FAIR: the EMBL-EBI training portal**

2 **Swan A L^{*1}, Broadbent A¹, Singh Gaur P¹, Mishra A¹, Gurwitz K¹, Mithani A¹, Morgan S L¹,**
3 **Malhotra G¹, Brooksbank C¹**

4 ¹EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton
5 CB10 1SD, UK

6 *** Correspondence:**

7 Anna Swan
8 annas@ebi.ac.uk

9 **Keywords: bioinformatics training, FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable)**
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11 **design.**

12 **Abstract**

13 EMBL-EBI provides a broad range of training in data-driven life sciences. To improve awareness
14 and access to training course listings and to make digital learning materials findable and simple to
15 use, the EMBL-EBI Training website, www.ebi.ac.uk/training, was redesigned and restructured.

16 To provide a framework for the redesign of the website, the FAIR (findable, accessible,
17 interoperable, reusable) principles were applied to both the listings of live training courses and the
18 presentation of on-demand training content. Each of the FAIR principles guided decisions on the
19 choice of technology used to develop the website, including the details provided about training and
20 the way in which training was presented.

21 Since its release the openly accessible website has been accessed by an average of 58,492 users a
22 month. There have also been over 12,000 unique users creating accounts since the functionality was
23 added in March 2022, allowing these users to track their learning and record completion of training.

24 Development of the website was completed using the Agile Scrum project management methodology
25 and a focus on user experience. This framework continues to be used now that the website is live for
26 the maintenance and improvement of the website, as feedback continues to be collected and further
27 ways to make training FAIR are identified. Here, we describe the process of making EMBL-EBI's
28 training FAIR through the development of a new website and our experience of implementing Agile
29 Scrum.

30 **1 Introduction**

31 As the need to analyze biological data continues to grow, so does the need for training in
32 bioinformatics. This extends beyond formal education delivered at university level, given continual
33 developments in methodologies, tools, and technologies used in this ever-changing field (Işık et al.,
34 2023).

35 EMBL-EBI provides a broad range of training in the field of data-driven life sciences, including
36 hands-on training for researchers to learn how to analyze their own data and training on EMBL-EBI
37 data services to help users get started with accessing, using, and submitting data. The training spans a

38 variety of formats including face-to-face courses on site at EMBL-EBI and at host organizations,
39 virtual courses conducted online, webinars, and on-demand self-paced tutorials and recorded
40 webinars, which are openly available on the EMBL-EBI Training website for anyone to access,
41 anytime.

42 Since 2016 (Wilkinson et al.), there has been a drive to make scientific data more usable and
43 reproducible using the FAIR data principles. The FAIR principles, Findable, Accessible,
44 Interoperable, and Reusable, revolve around clearly describing data, making data available in ways
45 that are accessible, and using formats that allow everyone who needs access to the data. These
46 principles can also be applied to training materials to make them more usable by both learners and
47 educators (Garcia et al., 2020; FAIR training handbook, 2023).

48 In 2021, aligned with EMBL-EBI's aim to make data FAIR, a new website was released which made
49 EMBL-EBI's training more FAIR. This included ensuring that information about our live courses
50 aligned with the FAIR principles. On-demand training and materials from live courses were already
51 being shared openly. However, users reported they were difficult to find and so focusing on
52 findability and taking a FAIR approach led to improved ways of sharing such training.

53 The training available on the EMBL-EBI Training website is divided into two sections, Live and On-
54 demand. The Live section includes all our training that happens at a specific time, including our face-
55 to-face and virtual courses, and webinars. On-demand training features all content that is accessible
56 to anyone, at any time through the website. This includes online tutorials, recorded webinars, course
57 materials and, most recently, collections of on-demand content on a specific topic and trainer pages,
58 which feature both EMBL trainers and those who join us from other companies and institutes.

59 **2 Materials and equipment**

60 The redevelopment of the EMBL-EBI training website began with the construction and socialization
61 of a vision for a new website that had users' requirements and user experience at its heart (Figure 1).
62 This vision was driven by the fact that, in 2019, the EMBL-EBI training website (actually two
63 separate sites, one for live and one for on-demand training, with a semi-automated catalog layer on
64 top) had evolved organically and had failed to scale adequately – either to the amount and complexity
65 of content that we were delivering, or to the user base, which was already in the range of 100s of
66 1000s of users per year. The complexity of the two separate websites also made navigation between
67 different types of training challenging for users and made findability of relevant content difficult, as
68 it was not possible to search for specific topics. These requirements aligned with the FAIR principles
69 and so applying these principles to the presentation and sharing of training and materials gave us a
70 focus for the website's development. There was also an additional driver to visually align the EMBL-
71 EBI Training website with the emerging EMBL visual framework (Hawkins, 2021), an open visual
72 standard that was being developed to provide consistency across EMBL's family of websites. Then
73 in 2020, after the start of the new website's development, the COVID-19 pandemic also provided a
74 different driver of change: our rapid shift to running courses virtually created new and urgent
75 requirements to support learners joining courses online.

76 The initial phase of website development focused on user needs for short, self-paced online tutorials.
77 Based on user research (see below), the platform to create tutorials needed to allow users to work
78 through or be able to drop into a single page of a tutorial from search engine results. It also needed to
79 be easy for course creators to add content, as this had previously been a bottleneck to creation and
80 updating of tutorials.

81 Several different e-learning platforms and content management systems (CMS) were researched and
82 tested, including those developed for higher education. However, we found that those specifically
83 designed for education or e-learning were too restrictive for the user journeys required. For example,
84 many e-learning platforms require users to complete a course in a linear journey, rather than having
85 the flexibility to start on the page most relevant to them and choose which other pages to move to
86 next. As we had clear evidence that only a small percentage of our users follow a linear learning path,
87 retaining this flexibility drove the choice of technology.

88 Based on this research, WordPress was chosen to create the online tutorials, primarily because of its
89 flexibility and ease of use for authors. Each tutorial is a WordPress Minisite, which is created and
90 edited through one central WordPress installation. It was also possible to add the H5P plugin to the
91 WordPress installation. H5P allows for the creation of interactive elements, such as quizzes,
92 interactive images, and drag-and-drop elements, which can be added into the online tutorials to make
93 the content more interactive (H5P, 2023).

94 While WordPress was chosen to create online tutorials, to provide the required flexibility, a second
95 CMS, Drupal, was selected to handle the information about courses (course metadata). This included
96 creation of course pages, which describe upcoming events, and front pages of online tutorials,
97 containing their metadata. Drupal was chosen because it is open-source, scalable and can handle a
98 large volume of structured data. It is also highly customizable and secure (Drupal, 2023). WordPress
99 could have been used for both functions; however, it would have required much customization,
100 whereas Drupal has many of the required features built in.

101 During development of the EMBL-EBI Training website, the EMBL visual framework, which is
102 designed to be FAIR and open, was also implemented. The Training website development also
103 contributed to the development of the EMBL visual framework, as new visual framework elements
104 were created to be used in the Training website (Hawkins, 2021).

105 **3 Methods**

106 **3.1 User requirements**

107 Before starting the website redesign, we conducted interviews and surveys with users of the previous
108 version of the EMBL-EBI Training website. Analytics showing how users interacted with the website
109 were also reviewed. This identified that some users had difficulties finding training courses and so
110 findability was identified as a key requirement.

111 The analytics also showed the different ways in which learners were accessing and using the on-
112 demand content. Some users found an online tutorial on the website and completed it from start to
113 finish; these users typically had a specific learning objective and used our tutorials to fulfill that
114 objective. Other users landed on a page within a tutorial from a search engine; these users were
115 primarily using our tutorials as a lookup service; the page of the tutorial that they landed on from
116 their internet search answered their question and they left the website. Google Analytics helped us to
117 review user journeys; however, understanding the journeys of online learners was not
118 straightforward, partly as a result of the way the website was designed to allow users the ability to
119 drop into the middle of online tutorials. Prior to development of the new website, some initial
120 experiments were done by making minor changes to the previous website, such as reducing the
121 amount of content on single pages, to see what impact they made to user engagement. These
122 experiments helped identify requirements for the new website and the two distinct user journeys
123 observed were important to consider for the website redesign. Users needed to continue to be able to

124 land within a page of a tutorial, not requiring them to start from page one as many e-learning courses
125 do. To do all this, the user interactions needed to remain flexible.

126 During the research phase, creators of the online tutorials were also interviewed. They reported that
127 they were put off creating courses in the previous website because they considered it to be time
128 consuming and difficult. Therefore, the choice of technology underpinning the new website needed to
129 work for both learners and content creators.

130 Finally, a handful of users in the EMBL-EBI Training team need an additional layer of access to
131 perform administrative and editorial functions, such as sharing aggregated user statistics with other
132 teams, creating template course mini-sites and giving course authors access to them, adding new live
133 courses to our listings, and ultimately publishing quality-checked content to the EMBL-EBI training
134 website. We therefore also considered our own needs and bottlenecks.

135 These three types of users – the learner, the course author and the training administrator – were
136 considered and consulted throughout the development process, and continue to be involved now that
137 we have moved into ‘maintenance mode’.

138 **3.2 Making training materials FAIR**

139 The FAIR principles can be applied to training materials to help in their use by learners and reuse by
140 other educators, by ensuring their findability and providing details about how they can be accessed
141 and reused. Findability of training was one of the main drivers of the redesign of the EMBL-EBI
142 Training website; however, throughout the process, all the FAIR principles guided decisions
143 regarding what types of information to include in our course descriptions (course metadata), how
144 content is displayed to users, and the potential for reuse of training materials by others, as explained
145 below.

146 **3.3 Findability of courses**

147 To ensure that live training can be registered for, or that online training can be used by learners, it
148 first needs to be findable (Garcia et al., 2020). This includes findability of both the website and the
149 courses listed within the website.

150 Before designing course pages, the required details about courses were first identified. The page
151 design then focused on the display of these course metadata. These metadata were also used to help
152 search engines identify a course page’s relevance. For live courses, each course page includes details
153 about the format, dates, cost, contact information, target audience, learning outcomes, organizers and
154 trainers, program, and details about how to apply or register, depending on the type of event. Online
155 tutorial front pages include similar details, such as target audience and learning outcomes, as well as
156 the creators, types of materials included, estimated time required, DOI, and details on how to get
157 started. During the initial planning phase of the website redevelopment, metadata for different types
158 of training format were identified and compared (Table 1). Previous community consensus, in
159 addition to information from users, guided the identification of necessary metadata (Schneider et al.,
160 2015).

161 One element of metadata that applied to on-demand content only is the digital object identifier (DOI).
162 In line with the FAIR training materials requirements of assigning a persistent identifier, all on-
163 demand content is assigned a DOI, as it has since 2013. A persistent identifier makes the materials
164 easier to cite and does not have the potential to change, unlike other identifiers, such as URLs (Garcia

165 et al., 2020). DOIs can also be linked to ORCID IDs for individuals, giving trainers more visibility
166 and recognition for the training materials that they contribute to (ORCID, 2023).

167 Many of the metadata listed are used to enhance the findability of courses through searching the
168 website. A prominent search box was added at the top of the front page of the website (Figure 2). The
169 search box uses the EBI Search functionality (Madeira et al., 2019), which allows users to search for
170 any terms they would like whilst providing autocomplete suggestions to help users identify suitable
171 search terms. These search terms are based on the metadata used to describe each course, including
172 the title and description; each course is also tagged with keywords about the course topic and any
173 EMBL-EBI data resources it relates to. Courses are also tagged with terms from EDAM, an ontology
174 of topics relating to bioscience data analysis and management (EDAM, 2023).

175 To further help users find what they were looking for, filters were added both to the course listings
176 and to the search results pages. For live courses the filters include the formats of events,
177 application/registration status, the year it ran/will take place, and its location. On-demand training
178 can also be filtered by format, as well as an estimated completion time.

179

180 Once a user has found training of interest, they may also wish to share it with others to help them
181 find suitable training. Therefore, all course pages, both in the Live and in the On-demand sections,
182 include share buttons to help users share content with others. There is also a playlist function to allow
183 users to share a selection of on-demand training with others (see below).

184 To make specific courses temporarily more findable, a featured courses section was also added to the
185 top of the homepage (Figure 2). Featured courses provide new users with a ‘taster menu’ of EMBL-
186 EBI courses and provide a way to highlight upcoming courses and new on-demand content.

187 Despite the addition of the search functionality and featured courses, feedback identified that it can
188 still be difficult for those new to bioinformatics to know where to start; for example, some learners
189 may not know what to search for. This prompted us to develop training Collections. Collections
190 contain online tutorials, recorded webinars, and short challenges on a single topic to help learners get
191 started. Example topics covered in Collections include introductory bioinformatics, exploring genetic
192 variation, and data-driven plant sciences.

193 The metadata and functionality described make training more findable either by searching the
194 website or through search engines. However, it is also important to make training more findable and
195 to reach a wider audience by listing courses in other registries, such as EMBL’s Courses and
196 Conferences Events listings (<https://www.embl.org/events/>) and ELIXIR’s TeSS (ELIXIR TeSS,
197 2023). To increase the accuracy and efficiency of this process an API is provided openly, and courses
198 are detailed using the BioSchemas standard (BioSchemas, 2023). The API is read by ‘consumer’ data
199 listings and courses are listed accordingly. Updates to the source data are propagated to consumer
200 course listings at differing intervals, including once a day and whenever a change is detected.

201 **3.4 Accessibility**

202 When applied to training, accessibility in the FAIR context focuses on ensuring that users have a
203 clear understanding of how they can access training (Garcia et al., 2020). For live training, this can be
204 achieved through a description of when and where courses are running, and how learners can apply
205 or register. For on-demand training, accessibility describes what users need to do to access the

206 content. This could include making it clear that there is no barrier to access, such as registration, and
207 that users do not need to be part of a specific group to gain access.

208 All EMBL-EBI on-demand training is openly available; no registration or login is required to access
209 it, including access to quizzes and other interactive content. A description of the recommended target
210 audience is included on each on-demand course; however, it is up to the user to decide whether they
211 fit within the target audience.

212 Nevertheless, users may choose to register for the website and log in. We added this functionality for
213 users who would like to track their progress through on-demand training. They can mark on-demand
214 training as favorites and see an overview of their in-progress and completed learning through a
215 bespoke ‘My learning’ page (Figure 3). Logged in users can also create their own playlists of on-
216 demand training, which can be shared with others, including those with no account, making it
217 possible for learners to share suggested courses with peers, or for educators to share required learning
218 with their students.

219 Attendees at our live courses are required to create an account and are given access to the course
220 handbook through their My learning page. All information and materials required for the course are
221 made available in the handbook. A modified version of the handbook, known as the course materials,
222 is made available through the On-demand section following the course, so that those not able to
223 attend may still benefit from the materials covered in the course, in a more flexible way. This
224 significantly enhances the reach of the course materials created for our live courses – an important
225 consideration given that (1) course materials are time consuming to produce and (2) demand for
226 places on live courses far outstrips supply.

227 Throughout development of the website, accessibility of content was also considered. This included
228 the use of alternative text for those using screen readers and reviewing color contrasts for color-
229 blindness (FAIR training handbook, 2023). On-demand training materials are also more accessible
230 for many compared with live training as they can be accessed anytime, from anywhere.

231 **3.5 Interoperability**

232 In the FAIR context, interoperability is concerned with the use of suitable formats and community
233 standards that can be accessed by anyone, for example, using open-source software and open file
234 formats in preference to proprietary software and file formats. This is directly applicable to training
235 as providing training materials in formats that many people are not able to use makes sharing the
236 materials useless for them (Garcia et al., 2020).

237 To ensure that all users can access and interact with training materials, all content, including the on-
238 demand courses, can be used on any internet browser. This includes videos and interactive content
239 developed using H5P. In the rare case that any other resources are required for the completion of an
240 online tutorial it is clearly stated on the front page.

241 The course materials are provided in a range of file formats owing to the range of topics, tools, and
242 trainers; however, all materials can be opened on any operating system, without the need for
243 specialist software. Where examples and exercises are provided, trainers are encouraged to use data
244 from open access data resources so that anyone can access both the data and the metadata to
245 reproduce the analyses.

246 **3.6 Reusability**

247 EMBL-EBI training materials and courses are provided for people to learn from; however, they are
248 also a key resource for other educators. Making training materials reusable by other educators avoids
249 repeated re-creation of similar materials, saving time and effort. However, materials do need to be
250 provided in a way that allows them to be reused providing necessary metadata, clearly describing
251 licenses, and using modifiable formats all enhance the reusability of training materials (Garcia et al.,
252 2020).

253 All the details used to describe on-demand content, such as target audience and learning outcomes,
254 also support educators in their reuse of materials. Educators, for example university lecturers or
255 bioinformatics trainers, are encouraged to reuse materials. Reuse could be as simple as a lecturer
256 sharing an online tutorial with students for them to complete as part of a course, or downloading
257 some slides initially used for a live course and repurposing them for a lecture.

258 For materials used during live courses, openly available sets of materials are created. These include a
259 page per lecture or practical session with a short overview and learning outcomes to provide context.
260 Individual files of a course's materials are available for download, or the materials from the whole
261 course can be downloaded from the EMBL-EBI Training FTP site.

262 All on-demand content also includes a release or update date so that anyone reusing the materials can
263 be confident that they are up to date and suitable for use.

264 To ensure that users know what they are allowed to do with the training content made available on
265 the EMBL-EBI Training website, the Creative Commons CC-BY license is shown on all pages of on-
266 demand content. CC-BY allows anyone to use or modify materials in any way they would like,
267 providing that they say where the materials came from (Creative Commons, 2023).

268 To further support both learners and educators in the use of materials, additional functionality has
269 been added to show the competencies that a learner would expect to develop by completing each
270 course. The competencies are taken from the Competency Hub, <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>, a
271 website that details various competency frameworks related to molecular life science and
272 bioinformatics careers. Each framework consists of a list of competencies. Each EMBL-EBI Training
273 course has a list of associated competencies (Figure 4). For bioinformatics competencies, the
274 archetype is the ISCB competency framework (Mulder et al., 2019; Gaeta et al., 2021; Mendonca et
275 al., 2022).

276 Applying the FAIR principles also makes the training materials we have more visible to those within
277 EMBL. The findability of on-demand content allows for the range of topics and formats of training to
278 be visible and potentially reused for different purposes and target audiences, and by different EMBL-
279 EBI trainers.

280 **3.7 Development process**

281 Before starting development, a lot of planning was undertaken; the vision for a new website was
282 socialized and the aims of the first sprints, concerned with redevelopment of online tutorials, were
283 identified.

284 To identify requirement details, we first wrote user stories that outlined different types of users and
285 their needs. We covered many different user journeys, considering the distinct requirements of
286 learners new to the website, trainers creating content, and those who would administer the site. This
287 process, which included web developers and user experience (UX) specialists, helped us to define

288 what we needed to build and who we needed to build it for, rather than getting distracted by the
289 capabilities and features of the software that we were using to build the site with. User stories define
290 a particular type of user and summarize their requirements in terms of what they must be able to do,
291 what they should be able to do, and what they could be able to do. The ‘must’ list provides the
292 requirements for the minimum viable product – what is needed for a viable website to be released. If
293 requirements from the ‘should’ and ‘could’ list were not included in the first release, they were
294 reviewed and potentially added during a later release of the website. This allowed the development
295 team to focus on what was strictly necessary, release early, test assumptions by soliciting feedback
296 from users, and improve the site responsively. Examples of user stories outlining the requirements of
297 users taking two different user journeys to the EMBL-EBI Training website are shown in Box 1; user
298 story 1 describes a user who lands on the homepage and user story 2 describes a user who lands part-
299 way through a course after following a link from a search engine result.

300 During both the development and the (ongoing) continuous improvement phases of the EMBL-EBI
301 Training website project, the Agile Scrum project management framework has been implemented
302 (Rising & Janoff, 2000). This involves a small development team, with clearly defined roles, working
303 in one- or two-week sprints to focus on a predefined set of tasks, which form the Sprint Goal.

304 The Sprint team included Developers, a Scrum Master, and a Product Owner (Schwaber &
305 Sutherland, 2020), drawn from members of the EMBL-EBI Training and Web development teams.
306 Prior to starting a Sprint, the team planned which tasks to take from the Product Backlog, the list of
307 all required tasks so far identified to develop the website, to move to the Sprint Backlog, those tasks
308 prioritized for the upcoming Sprint.

309 At the end of each Sprint there was a Demo to which all Stakeholders were invited, so that they could
310 see and provide feedback on the work completed during the Sprint and the plan for work prioritized
311 for the next Sprint. At this stage the Stakeholders were encouraged to make comments, give
312 feedback, or ask questions. At the end of the Sprint, the Sprint team also participated in the Sprint
313 Review, an opportunity to identify how the team was working together, through the identification of
314 what to continue, what to start doing and what to stop.

315 Throughout the development and gradual release of new website functionality, user testing was
316 undertaken, and feedback received from learners, trainers, and other stakeholders; however, it is also
317 important to allow for continual feedback. This is managed through email and a short feedback form
318 that is included at the end of all online tutorials, collections and sets of materials. In the feedback
319 form a rating is asked for, along with what the user liked about the course, what they think could be
320 improved and if/how they plan to apply what they have learnt. This information can be used to
321 further develop training and identify needs for future courses.

322 **4 Results**

323 The new website, developed using the FAIRification methods described, was released in February
324 2021 after a 3-year plus planning and development period. In the lead up to this full release, pilots
325 and beta releases of some content types were released and amended in light of user feedback; for
326 example, a single example of a newly designed on-demand course was released early on. Although
327 the redevelopment project has drawn to a conclusion, continuous improvement is ongoing. A
328 committee reviews and prioritizes tasks, and short sprints, undertaken by a more compact team, are
329 incorporated into our schedule.

330 Over the first two years after release, an average of 58,492 users per month have accessed the site,
331 including those who applied for live courses and users of on-demand training.

332 As of November 2023, the EMBL-EBI Training website contains nearly 200 recorded webinars, 81
333 online tutorials, nine collections, and 30 sets of course materials, as well as the live courses that are
334 listed on the website, including both those that are open for applications and past courses going back
335 to 2017. All follow the FAIR training principles.

336 Google Analytics showed that, in 2022, a total of 625,360 unique users accessed the EMBL-EBI
337 Training website and there was a total of 2,199,866 pageviews. Many users landed on specific course
338 pages directly from a search engine or were linked to the site from social media posts. Of these,
339 6.21% of visits to the website started on the website homepage; 65.5% of visits started on an online
340 tutorial page and 16.74% started by landing directly on a live course page. The remainder of visits
341 started by landing on course listings, search results, playlists created by users and pages about the
342 training offered.

343 After users had landed within the website there were also many searches using the EMBL-EBI
344 Training website search box; 28,375 searches were performed in 2022. The top 10 search terms used
345 in 2022 are shown in Table 2; they include both topics/methods in bioinformatics and the names of
346 EMBL-EBI data resources.

347 Analytics also showed that the 625,360 users who accessed the website in 2022 used a range of
348 different technologies. Table 3 provides an overview of the different types of browsers, operating
349 systems, and devices used by those accessing the website.

350 In March 2022, the registration functionality was added to the EMBL-EBI Training website. Since
351 then, 13,401 users from 167 countries have registered.

352 Through the voluntary short survey included at the end of each online tutorial, set of course materials
353 and collection, learners have shared what they thought of the courses and if they have any suggested
354 improvements. Although short surveys have been provided at the end of each online tutorial since the
355 launch of our on-demand training in 2011, since the redesign we have received much more feedback,
356 with a greater level of detail. An average of 106 online tutorial feedback forms are now being
357 completed each month. From a total of 3,182 completed surveys, 67.6% rated the tutorial or
358 collection they completed as “very good” or “excellent”. Many learners also shared how they plan to
359 apply what they have learnt. This ranges in theme, but often includes plans to access data from a data
360 resource, prepare data for submission to a resource, prepare for a new project they are working on,
361 teach others or use their learning to support their career development. Examples of quotes that
362 represent the major themes from online tutorial feedback forms are shown in Box 2.

363 **5 Discussion**

364 We have described the development of a new EMBL-EBI training website that places FAIR training
365 principles at the forefront of the design and development process. Here we discuss both the
366 methodology of developing the website and the results relating to users accessing the website in
367 terms of technology, FAIR principles, and the developmental process employed.

368

369 It has been difficult to make direct comparisons between the original and new EMBL-EBI Training
370 websites due to differing website structures and features (for example, the old website was essentially
371 split into two websites) and so we focus here on discussion of the new website. Furthermore, when
372 we launched the new website in beta, we continued to support the previous website; whilst this gave
373 our users a choice of platform, there was no means of telling whether individual users had made use
374 of both platforms.

375 **5.1 Technology**

376 At the start of the development process, we began by talking to users and reviewing website analytics
377 to get as accurate a picture as possible of how people were using the previous version of the EMBL-
378 EBI Training website. It was difficult to get a completely accurate picture of online user behavior as
379 we could talk directly to only a limited number of users; furthermore, user behavior and rationale is
380 not always clear from the analytics. This heavily impacted our choice of technology. It also drew us
381 towards considering different types of users - those who deliberately seek out learning materials
382 versus those that land by chance in the middle of a course whilst looking up facts. Both are entirely
383 valid uses of our training content. It was therefore important to support both types of users. With only
384 6.21% of visits to the new website starting on the front page, it is clear this flexibility has been
385 retained.

386 Flexibility in how users access our training has been retained by choosing two web development
387 platforms that are not specifically designed for training or education, but that are key components of
388 EMBL's web development toolkit. Whilst this decision meant investing web developer time to build
389 and maintain the bespoke platform, this approach has allowed us to use components developed for
390 other parts of the EMBL website, contribute new elements to the EMBL visual framework (Hawkins,
391 2021), and make use of common infrastructure and content, including EMBL-EBI's powerful search
392 engine, and information about trainers and course authors who are members of EMBL personnel. The
393 need for this flexibility was supported by the results, which show that the majority of website users
394 land directly into an online tutorial or live course page from search engine results, direct links, or
395 social media links.

396 For development of online tutorials, WordPress has proved to be simple for content creators,
397 enabling them to draft and collaboratively edit their tutorials in common word processing tools then
398 simply copy and paste content into the platform once it has passed our editorial quality control
399 process. As a result, more EMBL members of personnel are now actively involved in creating and
400 regularly updating course materials.

401 Including the H5P plugin in the installation of WordPress opened up many possibilities for adding
402 interactivity to online tutorials. Elements such as interactive images have been used frequently to
403 help learners explore a data resource in a structured way from within the tutorial. Other interactive
404 elements, such as quizzes, crosswords, and drag-and-drop questions, are helping learners to stay
405 engaged and test their own learning (Box 2). Interactive H5P elements are created using simple forms
406 and so content creators have been able to create interactivity, without specialist technical knowledge.
407 This is helping us to meet user demand for more interactivity.

408 **5.2 FAIR principles**

409 Applying the FAIR principles to the presentation of course details, on-demand training, and materials
410 provided a structure to the redesign of the EMBL-EBI Training website which focused on how users

411 would be able to find, access and use content. Keeping this structure at the forefront of design and
412 content decisions helped identify the detail and functionality required by users.

413 The first aim of using the FAIR principles to guide development of the website was to make sure the
414 training was findable. Our training content had grown organically since the launch of the EMBL-EBI
415 training program in 2007, and our previous platform provided little or no scope to organize training
416 in more intuitive ways, especially given the expanding and evolving nature of the content, and no
417 straightforward means of incorporating a free-text search engine. The results show that many users
418 are finding training, some directly from search engine results and others through the website's
419 internal search. One of the main requirements for making training findable was the inclusion of
420 search functionality, including the search box on the front page of the website and at the top of both
421 the Live and On-demand listings. The results show that users are searching for a variety of terms
422 relevant to the training available and that most of these searches use the suggested autocomplete
423 keywords (Table 2). These keywords appear when users start typing their search. This helps users to
424 understand the topics they might expect to find in our training platform and reduces issues with
425 spelling mistakes in search terms. Nevertheless, users are not limited to searching for the keywords
426 that have been associated with available courses. Reviewing the most popular search terms can also
427 help us to identify gaps in the training available.

428 The featured courses, a short list of what's new or recently opened for registration, was also added to
429 the top of the front page of the website to support findability of new courses. From the analytics we
430 have observed that featuring a new course does drive users to explore it. Feedback from users during
431 testing also identified that featured courses help to raise awareness of the type of training and topics
432 available on the site. This was useful to discover during testing as it highlighted the importance of
433 covering a range of topics and training formats in the featured courses section. Comments from users
434 who claimed not to know where to start or what topics were available also led to the development of
435 themed collections (Box 2), selections of on-demand training on a specific topic, with a suggested
436 learning pathway that takes the user from the more basic content through to the more advanced, or
437 more niche applications. Feedback on these collections has shown that users have found it useful to
438 know where to start on a topic, even if they do not complete the whole collection. Online question
439 and answer webinars have also been run on specific collections to give learners an opportunity to ask
440 questions that arise from working through the collections. The development of further collections is
441 now planned.

442 Throughout development of the website, it was clear that keeping the on-demand training open and
443 accessible by all was a necessity, in line with EMBL's open science policy
444 (<https://www.embl.org/about/open-science/>). However, to offer learners functionality for tracking
445 learning it was necessary to require registration and logging in. The accessibility of content is made
446 clear on the initial registration page where it is stated that registration is not required to access
447 content, but instead to keep track of learning. With a small subset of users, 13,401, having registered
448 for the site it seems clear to users that registration is not required, but instead an optional extra for
449 those who want to track their learning, through their bespoke My learning page, a personalized
450 learning profile that can be used to provide evidence of their learning (Figure 3).

451 During development, it was also important to keep interoperability of training at the forefront of how
452 the training could be completed. The results show that users are using a range of internet browsers,
453 operating systems, and types of devices demonstrating the importance for interoperability of training
454 materials (Table 3). As further training materials are added to the website and new tools, data types,
455 and file types become common in the ever-changing field of bioinformatics it will be important to

456 keep interoperability in mind to ensure that exercises can be completed by everyone, regardless of
457 their access to specific tools and technologies.

458 For re-use of training materials by other educators, it is difficult to know how many are using the
459 materials for this purpose. There have been comments in feedback forms that show educators are
460 repurposing materials (Box 2); however, as materials are openly available there is no requirement for
461 educators to report on their use in this way. This makes it easier for them to be reused; however, it
462 would be useful to receive more feedback from educators so that we can support them further and
463 ensure that our materials are presented in a way that is effective for them. Applying the FAIR
464 principles also provided us with an opportunity to think about how we can reuse our own materials;
465 we were able to more easily review what on-demand training we had available and reuse it in other
466 ways. Doing this led to the creation of Collections, which make the most of materials we already
467 have available by guiding learners to them in a format that sets training in the context of a broader
468 topic and supports the user to work through the courses from basic principles to more advanced
469 training. Reusability of materials is also important for EMBL's trainers; making materials easily
470 findable across a large organization has stimulated repurposing of existing content and reduced
471 'reinvention of the wheel'.

472 Assigning relevant competencies to each course is a more recent addition to the EMBL-EBI Training
473 site (Figure 4). The inclusion of competencies associated with each course is supporting users to
474 discover the Competency Hub where they can learn more about the specific bioinformatics-related
475 competencies and what they may want to focus their learning on to progress in their career. The
476 competencies should also help educators who wish to use materials in their own teaching as they give
477 a short overview of the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that they might expect their students to gain
478 by completing a given piece of training.

479 **5.3 Development process**

480 Prior to starting the development of the website, the time spent writing user stories was extremely
481 valuable for identifying what different users would require, the minimum requirements for releasing
482 sections of the website, and prioritization of work. Including both web developers and UX specialists
483 at this early stage helped us to start working together in partnership, bringing different ideas and
484 experiences, and smoothing the way for the start of the development process. The exercise of
485 identifying the metadata required for each type of training prior to development also helped us to
486 ensure we covered all the required information and provided a focus to start discussing design and
487 user experience.

488 The use of the Agile Scrum methodology provided a framework for a new team, comprising web
489 developers and training practitioners, to work together on the development of the EMBL-EBI
490 Training website.

491 This methodology lends itself well to the development of an online training resource, as it provides a
492 structured way to include all stakeholders at defined steps in the process. It secured the commitment,
493 at predefined times, from all members of the core development team, who worked together to achieve
494 a shared goal. Those who were stakeholders but did not have the time (or the remit) to participate
495 actively in sprints still had a well-defined and rapidly understood channel for receiving updates and
496 providing feedback, in the form of sprint demos. Recording and open sharing of the demos within
497 EMBL allows anyone with an interest in progress on the project to catch up. The iterative process of
498 sprints ensures that something tangible is released and presented at the Demo at the end of each
499 sprint. At that stage it can then be viewed and commented on by others. The release may not be

500 visible publicly, but internal Stakeholders have the opportunity to see the results of the development
501 process at regular intervals, allowing for required changes to be identified before a lot of time has
502 been spent developing functionality that may not be suitable. Adhering to Scrum allowed for the
503 developments and choices made by the sprint team to be visible to the Stakeholders and gave those
504 Stakeholders the opportunity to provide input on the website development without being involved in
505 the details discussed during the sprints. Working in short sprints also gave the development team the
506 protected time to focus on the project without being required to shift focus to other work.

507 Initially, at the start of the development process, it was difficult to determine what was possible in
508 terms of development in the set sprint length. However, after progressing through the first sprints and
509 reviewing the tasks achieved, the team became adept at predicting what was possible within one
510 sprint. Identifying sprint aims became an easier and more accurate process and items chosen for each
511 sprint's backlog became more achievable.

512 The iterative process of sprints helped us to incorporate new ways of being FAIR. As we continued
513 with the development, new ways of making the training FAIR became evident and we were able to
514 include these in subsequent sprint plans. This flexible, iterative process also helped us respond
515 rapidly to changes in course delivery as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. During this time, there
516 were significant changes in how we delivered live courses: within three months of the first
517 'lockdown', our previously face-to-face courses were being delivered virtually. This had an impact
518 on how we provided course information and training content to our live-course delegates, as we
519 wrestled with the need to reduce live contact time (primarily to deal with the twin challenges of time-
520 zone differences and 'zoom fatigue'). Due to the format of sprints, including the potential for
521 reprioritization at the start of each sprint, we were able to adapt to these changing requirements and
522 priorities during the website development. The outcome of this was the development of our web-
523 based course handbooks, which are provided to learners in the lead up to each course and provide
524 access to all the content that delegates need during a course. These handbooks are provided only to
525 registered participants. After each course, public sets of course materials are derived from the course
526 handbooks.

527 The Sprint Reviews were also a very important part of the sprint process, especially at the start of the
528 project. Having a structured process to identify what was working well or to identify new ways of
529 working together was very useful. While it was most beneficial towards the beginning of the project,
530 it continued to be useful for ensuring the team worked well together throughout the project,
531 especially as some members of the sprint team changed.

532 At frequent intervals throughout the redesign, we ran user testing to learn how others interact with
533 the website. This was essential in understanding how new users would interact with the new
534 functionality, whether they found it intuitive, and leading us in making improvements prior to public
535 release.

536 **5.4 Further work**

537 Although the major restructuring and redesign of the EMBL-EBI training website is complete,
538 websites are dynamic resources requiring ongoing maintenance and updates, and there is always
539 more that can be done to improve the FAIRness of our training. We will continue to collect feedback
540 from users, both trainees and trainers, to improve the website's functionality and FAIRness. There
541 are also plans to continue introducing further interactivity and practical exercises into the on-demand
542 training to help learners stay engaged and gain more hands-on experience. The feedback from online

543 tutorials and collections will continue to help improve content and identify topics and formats which
544 are popular.

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589 **7 Conflict of Interest**

590 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
591 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

592 **8 Author Contributions**

593 Swan A L: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration; Broadbent
594 A: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration; Singh Gaur P:
595 Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration; Mishra A:
596 Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Methodology; Gurwitz K: Writing – review & editing;
597 Mithani A: Writing – review & editing; Morgan S L: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization,
598 Investigation, Supervision; Malhotra G: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Supervision;
599 Brooksbank C: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Supervision.

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614 **12 Data Availability Statement**

This article is a preprint.

615 The training described in this article, including metadata, are openly <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/>.
 616 EMBL's Visual Framework is <https://stable.visual-framework.dev/>. Information about Licensing of
 617 EMBL-EBI data resources is also available <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/>.

618 **Table 1.** Metadata identified for different training types during initial planning of the EMBL-EBI
 619 Training website redevelopment.

Face-to-face course	Webinar/webinar recording	Online tutorial front page
Title	Title	Title
Subtitle	Subtitle	Subtitle
Start date/time	Start date/time	Date of last update
End date/time	End date/time	
Time zone	Time zone	
Duration	Length of webinar	Time to complete
Venue		
Room		
Registration opens		
Registration deadline		
Acceptance notification date		
Register interest email		
Sponsor/In association with...	Sponsor/In association with...	Sponsor/In association with...
Provider	Provider	Provider
Participation (eg open application with selection)	Participation (eg first come, first serve)	

		Image
Contact person	Contact person	Contact email
Scientific Organizer	Organizer	
Trainer details	Trainer details	Authors
Registration fee	Registration fee	
Registration information	Registration information	
Long description (long text field)	Long description (long text field)	Subject matter overview
Target audience	Target audience	Target audience
		Technical requirements
Learning outcomes	Learning outcomes	Learning outcomes
Programme		Course contents
Learning context (e.g. face-to-face, hybrid)		
EDAM tags	EDAM tags	EDAM tags
Keywords	Keywords	Keywords
Registration link	Registration link	
Capacity	Capacity	
	Event capacity full	
	DOI	DOI
Materials link	Materials link	

	Link to recording	Link to first online tutorial page
License	License	License
Social media links	Social media links	Social media links
Language	Language	Language
Submitter	Submitter	Submitter
Additional information		

620

621 **Box 1.** Example user stories describing two different user journeys to access the EMBL-EBI Training
622 website.

User story 1: potential learner/first-time visitor

As a (potential) Learner landing on the EMBL-EBI Training homepage
I want to gain a broad overview of EMBL-EBI’s training offering
So that I can explore the content further to identify the training that best meets my needs

I must be able to:

- Recognise that I have landed on EMBL-EBI’s training ‘shop window’
- Be able to find relevant training in the format that best suits them
- Rapidly enter the ‘catalogue’ to discover the scope of training on offer - in terms of topic, format, level of engagement required, and timescale
- Rapidly discover the values associated with EMBL-EBI training
- Access new and promoted content quickly
- Navigate back to the EMBL-EBI homepage
- Have links to social media accounts
- Sign up to the EMBL newsletter or our social media streams for regular updates
- Contact a person if they have questions

I should be able to:

- Learn about who EMBL-EBI’s regular trainers are on the training faculty page
- Link to the team homepage
- Tell me how I can benefit from the training on offer (knowledge, competencies)

I could be able to:

- Access testimonials from past learners
- Have a live Twitter feed/widget

User story 2: accidental learner/fact finder

As a user who has landed on a course page from a Google search
I want to find the fact that I was looking up and rapidly identify the broader context in which it's set
So that I can evaluate whether there is further useful information for me in this unknown website I have just landed in

I must be able to:

- Navigate to the beginning of the course
- See my lookup content in the context of surrounding contents (i.e. view the course contents page)
- Navigate to the EMBL-EBI Training homepage from the page I landed on
- Figure out quickly that this is part of the EMBL-EBI website

I should be able to:

- Find other content containing my lookup term, ideally ranked according to relevance

623

624 **Table 2.** Top 10 search terms used in the EMBL-EBI Training website search box in 2022

Search term	Frequency of search term use in 2022
Next-generation sequencing	1535
Metabolomics	1155
Cheminformatics	836
GWAS	705
Molecular modelling	637
Single cell	625
Biocuration	599
Uniprot	577
Metagenomics	495
Transcriptomics	488

625

626 **Table 3.** Distribution of browser, operating system, and device user by users of EMBL-EBI Training
627 website in 2022

Browser	Users
---------	-------

Chrome	68.7%
Safari	16.1%
Edge	6.01%
Firefox	5.82%
Other	3.38%
Operating system	
Windows	44.0%
Android	22.2%
Macintosh	21.1%
iOS	9.72%
Linux	2.72%
Other	0.37%
Device	
Desktop	68.7%
Mobile	30.9%
Tablet	0.89%

628

629 **Box 2.** Example responses from the short survey included at the end of each online tutorial.

<p>What did you like about the course? “I learned a lot; this type of challenge-based learning works really well for me!” “Interactive elements and clear structure.” “Guided examples were a great way to engage” “The on-demand training is flexible.” “If you're a learner then this is the right path to learn about bioinformatics.”</p> <p>What could be improved? “More videos of live demos.” “More interactive tasks and quizzes.” “More examples.”</p> <p>Will you apply what you have learnt in your research/work? If yes, please tell us how. “Accessing UniProt data programmatically” “I will submit my results to the BIA [BioImage Archive] with sufficient metadata” “In teaching Bioinformatics at College”</p>
--

“I’m studying a bioinformatics course and this was a good base introduction to the subject.”
“I’m a student that wants to pursue a career in this area.”

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633 **Figure 1.** Initial vision for the new EMBL-EBI training website.

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Figure 2. EMBL-EBI Training homepage showing search box and featured courses. The homepage can be accessed at www.ebi.ac.uk/training.

On-demand training

Favourite (12) **In progress (8)** Completed (6)

Online tutorial
Bioinformatics for the terrified

38%

Resume

An introduction to the science of bioinformatics
Last page completed: Using ontologies to provide controlled vocabularies

▼ My results

Content	Score	Maximum score	Finished
Using ontologies to provide controlled vocabularies	6	6	Wed Nov 01 2023
Check your learning	3	5	Mon Nov 27 2023

BioImage Archive

Online tutorial
BioImage Archive

31%

Resume

Quick tour
Last page completed: Submitting data to the BioImage Archive

640
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643

Figure 3. In-progress On-demand training section of a My learning page.

Course overview Programme How to apply **Competencies**

Competency frameworks define a core set of competencies required by professionals working in a specific field.

Visit the [Competency Hub](#) to learn more about what competencies are and to view a range of competency frameworks, career profiles, and training resources to support career development in the life sciences.

Competency framework for Students and professionals in computational biology developed by ISCB

This course provides learning to support the development of the following ISCB framework competencies:

- A3: Work at depth in at least one technical area aligned with the life sciences
- B3: Prepare life science data for computational analysis
- D3: Use data science methods suitable for the size and complexity of the data
- E3: Manage own and others' data according to community standards and principles
- F3: Make appropriate use of bioinformatics tools and resources
- H3: Make appropriate and efficient use of scripting and programming languages
- L3: Work effectively in teams to accomplish a common goal
- M3: Engage in continuing professional development in bioinformatics

[View details of these competencies in the Competency Hub.](#)

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Figure 4. Example of competencies attributed to a training course.